

COMPONENTS OF IMPROVING THE PERFORMING COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS THROUGH THE USE OF THE AFGHAN RUBAB

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the components of improving the performing competence of future music teachers using the Afghan rubab, including analytical and prognostic tasks, cognitive-research tasks, organizational and managerial tasks, communication and creative tasks, as well as reflective problems.*

Keywords: *afghan rubab, components, performance, concept, research, teacher, future music teacher.*

It is important to note that during the study of the motivational component for engaging in musical activity related to performance skills on musical instruments, we recognized the importance of improving the performing skills of future music teachers. Competencies, emotional-volitional qualities, motivation, and reflective cognitive qualities—all these factors influence the development of the individual characteristics of the future music teacher and their mastery in performing on musical instruments.

In accordance with the period from the formation of individual characteristics of the future music teacher, such as abilities, emotional-volitional qualities, motivation, reflexive, cognitive, to their improvement [2]. In the process of performing any activity, individual characteristics of a person develop and turn into new personal developments [4].

In light of the aforementioned information based on the opinions of scientists in the field of music pedagogy, we came to a certain decision that individual-personal characteristics (musical abilities, emotional-volitional qualities, motivation) of the future music teacher in the performance of playing musical instruments will develop, and a new personal formation will be developed lim - a musical instrument has its own characteristics, for example, performance skills.

As previously mentioned on the theoretical provisions outlined above, we consider the music performance competition as a systemic organization, a complex multi-level structure functioning as a set of personal, cognitive functions, interaction and mutual influence of the individual. can be defined as an integrated education. It is in such a process that the activity and reflexive components, the level of their formation allow the future music teacher to effectively perform activities on musical instruments.

With respect to the personal component includes: musical abilities, emotional-volitional qualities, as well as the motivation of the personality of the future music teacher, which develops in the process of playing a musical instrument. We determined these components based on the analysis of the individual characteristics of the future music teacher necessary for mastering musical instruments. It was taken into account that the personal component is of great importance within the framework of the research topic, as the leading component in improving the skills of playing musical instruments of the future music teacher.

In terms of the cognitive-activity component represented special musical-performing knowledge and skills that ensure the practical implementation of playing musical instruments.

It can be observed that the idea of performing and interpreting a musical work is realized thanks to the system of performing musical instruments [2]. No matter how important the role of musical abilities is in the creative process of musical performance, abilities alone are not enough to create a full-fledged work. The quality of performance, as well as the productivity of musical performance, largely depends on knowledge and skills, which are different aspects of human activity. Often, a lack of knowledge, skills and qualifications is perceived by professionals as a lack of the necessary skills [3]. "...if the performer is not armed with the necessary qualifications, knowledge, skills, the process of creative musical performance will be so low [1]. The whole complexity of performing musical activity is that the activity is based on knowledge, but when assimilating already known knowledge and creating new ideas and images, completely different mental processes occur [5].

This is evidenced by the reflexive component includes critical and heuristic principles and serves as a source of new knowledge. Realizing the unconscious, cognizing the unknown, reasoning takes as its subject a critical analysis of knowledge about it, its content and methods of cognition. According to some scientists who conducted research in the field of pedagogy, they say that "the leading cognitive function of thinking is realized as an understanding of the means of solving problems by determining the methods of searching for them with the help of additional mental actions." The main task of the reaction is to ensure the stability of the inclusion of the "I" in this process [4].

It is essential to consider that reflection was considered an important component of the performing skills of a future music teacher when playing a musical instrument. This component regulates the inclusion of self-management mechanisms in the process of musical performance, such as self-assessment, self-analysis, self-control, which helps the future teacher to adequately understand and evaluate this process.

In pursuit of understanding, the competition of musical instrument performance skills as a personal education of a future music teacher is a single integral structure that cannot exist without its components; allows the future music teacher to realize himself as a subject of playing musical instruments; music education allows a bachelor's student to improve professionally; includes verifiable characteristics that allow to evaluate the activities of a future music teacher; allows a music teacher to improve his professional skills.

As previously mentioned that in order to solve the problem of improving the musical instrument playing skills of future music teachers, the following is necessary. These are: 1) identifying the leading pedagogical approaches to solving this problem; 2) developing a model for improving the musical instrument playing skills of future music teachers; 3) identifying pedagogical conditions for effectively improving the musical instrument playing skills of future music teachers.

In the process of theoretical understanding of the problem, we assumed that if the following set of conditions is met, the process of improving the musical instrument playing skills of future music teachers will continue more successfully within the framework of applied components. 1) the task is to organize the performing activities of future specialists on musical instruments based on the technology of professional performance; 2) dialogize the process of improving the skills of

playing musical instruments; 3) give a reflexive-positional definition of a future specialist in playing musical instruments.

In this section, we will consider the methodological aspects of improving the musical performance competition of a future music teacher based on the pedagogical conditions identified within the framework of the model presented in its theoretical justification.

In accordance with the methodological system or complex methodology is understood as a method of discovery or teaching-self-education, education-self-education, development-self-education, the content is understood as the internal unity of mechanisms, methods and means.

Taking into account the peculiarities of the implementation of the first condition, the organization of performing activities on musical instruments of future music teachers based on these components.

The system of tasks for improving the components of mastery of musical instruments, the competencies of the future music teacher in the organization of musical and performing activities, the musical instrument of future music teachers by students of pre-graduate education in music education we understand how to solve tasks specifically aimed at improving management skills. When developing such a set of tasks, we must solve the following problems: 1) classification of tasks; 2) methods of their presentation. Currently, there are many different classifications of tasks of professional and pedagogical scientific research. Based on these groups, we developed a set of tasks aimed at improving the components of individual skills (analytical and prognostic, cognitive and search, organizational and regulatory, communicative and creative, reflexive).

Type	Components of musical performance tasks	Analysis of the characteristics of musical performance tasks
I	Analytical and prognostic tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tasks aimed at setting a goal and improving the problem of musical performance; - tasks aimed at deciphering the musical text and musical terminology; - tasks aimed at logical understanding of the musical text; - tasks aimed at predicting performance (creating an artistic image);
II	Cognitive and search tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tasks aimed at discovering the characteristic features of style; - tasks of improving knowledge in the field of musical culture through creative application in practice; - tasks aimed at choosing the optimal technique;
III	Organizational and normative tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tasks on organizing the educational activities of students of a reproductive, heuristic and creative nature in music lessons; - tasks aimed at organizing the stages of work on a musical piece; - tasks aimed at organizing rehearsal activities (independent study tasks, exercises in the concert hall);

IV	Communication and creative tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tasks aimed at the problem of finding and making new performance decisions on musical instruments; - tasks aimed at developing a creative strategy for the activity of a musical instrument; - tasks of activating the personal and value attitude of the performer to the content of a musical piece; - tasks to actualize the artistic and mental actions of students, emotional attitude to music;
V	Reflexive tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tasks for self-knowledge, analysis of the current situation; - not success, but tasks aimed at reflecting on one's musical and performing success; - tasks aimed at monitoring and analyzing the dynamics of musical performance (assessing the conformity of musical performance with the composer's idea).

How are tasks presented? It should be considered as a “task” given to the student to convey, that is, solve, the educational task. A task that can be defined as a task requires not only musical performance, but also pedagogical actions, both intellectual and practical. In order to realize the ultimate goal of the entire sequence of actions to solve such a sequence of tasks, we have formulated a central task that directs the student to the final result (performing a creative, expressive, technically flawless musical work). We have clearly defined the “trajectory” of movement towards this result [5].

The logic of performing a central task (integrative task) aimed at the final result always includes solving certain tasks:

- 1) getting acquainted with the musical work;
- 2) studying sources of information about the musical work (its author, genre, style);
- 3) understanding the artistic and sound image of the work;
- 4) developing a concept for completing the task;
- 5) linking the image of the medium with the artistic-sound image, developing the technical details of the composition;
- 6) synthetically differentiated scope of the task;
- 7) preparation of the work performed in the Afghan rubab for the stage (high-level synthesis);
- 8) analysis and evaluation of the performance of this musical work.

In terms of each subtask of such an integrative problem is divided into a number of subtasks. For example, to solve a subtask such as “developing the performance concept of the work”, the student must understand the subject of the problem and solve it himself based on a comprehensive analysis of the text using the following methods:

a holistic analysis of a musical work, a method of contributing to the enrichment of knowledge of students of the bachelor's degree in music education. The method involves obtaining a comparative description of the styles of composers of close and opposite creative directions. The most characteristic aspect of the adoption of generalization involves identifying stylistic features. For example, on the basis of generalizing the characteristic stylistic features of the prelude in works

performed in the Afghan rubab, undergraduate students had an idea of the main directions of the stylistic trends of music in the first half of the 19th century;

the method of stylistic deduction, which consists in finding general patterns of style, genre in a specific sample (work). The musical genre is closely related to the historical period and its specific themes. The use of this method entails the need to acquire knowledge about the laws of musical art, the relationship between the past and the present in culture, the philosophy of the era in which the composer lived, aesthetic and professional, pedagogical views;

the method of harmonic analysis is associated with a detailed analysis of “harmony, melody, polyphony, Afghan rubab texture” [1]. This helps to understand the logic of the development and disclosure of the content of a musical composition. A careful study of the harmonic structure clarifies the development processes of the work, determines the internal auditory image of each aspect of the image, teaches to understand and evaluate the role of musical instruments and means of expression in the artistic whole;

the method of differential analysis of the form implies analytical-aural and performing study of the most important “coordinates” of the musical form: melody, time-rhythm, harmony, dynamics, timbre, texture. It helps the musician to establish the main division of the work, to reveal the nature of each part, as well as its specific features and characteristics of its connection with the previous, subsequent and whole, and to improve it verbally. It determines the direction of movement of sounds, the location of the climax points, the features of the dynamic and tempo profile, the general modulation plan of the work, and reveals the main technical difficulties, the work on which requires special attention from the performer;

the method of detailed performing analysis of the text of the work. Its main direction is the study of the system of artistic goals and the means of achieving them. It follows that analysis does not mean only the acquisition of knowledge. It represents the closest combination of understanding and skill, the harmony of the knowledge and technical skills of the performer of music, the harmony of the artistic concept of the interpreter with the means of its embodiment. It is this “skill of understanding” that can be called the standard of correct orientation, understanding of an object or phenomenon. Without it, it is impossible to achieve the heights of knowledge that allow us to perceive “the being of being in the integrity of its idea”.

For this reason, solving specific problems related to the implementation of various types of analysis of the improvement of the performing competence of future music teachers using the Afghan rubab should help the student to develop a performance concept for each specific musical work allows us to solve the problem of developing a musical instrument. According to the research topic of the performing concept of the composition, which serves as an indicative basis for the performance of musical instruments, we have identified three types of orientation according to the doctrine. These are:

a description of the movement without instructions on a specific example (method of demonstration) or the methodology for its implementation (a system of incomplete directions);

complete and detailed instructions on the correct execution of the movement;

the indicative basis of the movement is formed on the basis of knowledge independently obtained by the listeners.

The most effective is a generalized and complete orientation, which is formed independently by the student. A generalized orientation is revealed when the performer can apply the existing elements of mastery - knowledge and skills - in each new work prepared for execution

[7]. A complete orientation should include the main features of all three components that make up an integral performing movement. These are: artistic image, sound image and media image. The student's independence in constructing the directional part of the performance movement can be achieved if the teacher can determine in a conversation with the student of the music direction what the artistic image should be, how it should sound and how it should be in each specific case (in the case of musical performance), then he will learn what technical means can be used to achieve this. Expressing the orientation, expressing the character, mood of the music, building a form, organizing the rhythm, etc., that is, in a broad sense, fully covers the intonation of the text of the instrumental music work. These discussions concern not only the main components of the work, but also many details. For example, when preparing to perform a soundtrack piece performed on an Afghan rubab in a play by Alisher Navoi, the teacher draws the student's attention to understanding the essence of the entire work and examples of the performance style.

In general, the logic of solving each problem is subject to a generalized algorithm that includes three main stages:

- 1) the indicative stage, which begins with the analysis and development of the performance concept;
- 2) the performance stage, which is associated with the implementation of the performance intention of the author's work, its stage embodiment;
- 3) the reflexive stage, which is associated with the analysis of the student's actions (self-analysis) at each stage of solving the problem (here we used the algorithm for entering the reflexive position described above).

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